

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL

The introduction of information technology and e-health care system in the medical field helps clinical experts to provide better health care to the patient. This study addresses the problems of segmentation of abnormal brain tissues and normal tissues such as gray matter (gm), white matter (wm), and cerebrospinal fluid (csf) from magnetic resonance (mr) images using feature extraction technique and support vector machine (svm) classifier .The tumor is basically an uncontrolled growth of cancerous cells in any part of the body, whereas a brain tumor is an uncontrolled growth of cancerous cells in the brain. A brain tumor can be benign or malignant. The benign brain tumor has a uniformity in structure and does not contain active (cancer) cells, whereas malignant brain tumors have a nonuniformity (heterogeneous) in structure and contain active cells. The gliomas and meningiomas are the examples of low-grade tumors, classified as benign tumors and glioblastoma and astrocytomas are a class of high-grade tumors, classified as malignant tumors.To detect infected tumor tissues from medical imaging modalities, segmentation is employed.

1.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY

The system decides whether the brain has tumor or is it tumor-free from the MR image using combined technique of FCM Clustering algorithm and Convolutional Neural Network using Deep Learning. In the first stage the input image is converted to grey scale using binary thresholding and the spots are detected. Brain tumor is an accumulation of anomalous tissue in the brain. Tumors are primarily classified into malignant and benign when they develop. It can be life threatening hence it is important to recognize and identify the presence of tumors in brain image. The brain image can be detected from the MR image whether it has tumor or is it tumor-free using combined technique of FCM and deep learning techniques. In the first stage the input image is converted to grey scale using binary thresholding and the spots are detected. The recognized spots are represented in terms of their intensities to distinguish between the normal and tumor brain. The set of feature extracted are later characterized by using FCM clustering algorithm, then the tumor recognition is done using deep learning techniques. Brain tumours are frequently referred to as cancerous also known as malignant or non-cancerous termed as benign cells in the brain. There is a need to improve the standard of the brain tumor MR images and make these images suited for future processing by imaging modalities. It also helps to improve parameters of MR images.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Image processing aims to transform an image into digital form and performs some process on it, to get an enhanced image or take some utilized information from it. Image quality can refer to the level of accuracy in which different imaging systems capture, process, store, compress, transmit and display the signals that form an image. Processing aims at assessing and improving the quality of data to allow for reliable statistical analysis. Contrast Resolution measure is used in medical imaging to quantify the quality of acquired images. The central aim of Super-Resolution (SR) is to generate a higher resolution image from lower resolution images. The median filter is a non-linear digital filtering technique, often used to remove noise from an image or signal. Median filter reduces the variance of the intensities in the image. Median filter is a spatial filtering operation, so it uses a 2D mask that is applied to each pixel in the input image. This is operation of a 3x3 Median Filter for a sample image neighborhood. This filtering technique is used for noise removal from images and signals. It is very crucial in the image processing field as it is well known for the preservation of edges during noise removal. The goal of image enhancement is to improve the usefulness of an image for a given task such as providing a more subjectively pleasing image for human viewing. Enhancements make it easier for visual interpretation and understanding of imagery.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 THE MULTIMODAL BRAIN TUMOR IMAGE SEGMENTATION BENCHMARK (BRATS)

The Multimodal Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Benchmark (BRATS) is organized in conjunction with the MICCAI 2012 and 2013 conferences. Twenty state-of-the-art tumor segmentation algorithms were applied to a set of 65 multi-contrast MR scans of low- and high-grade glioma patients—manually annotated by up to four raters—and to 65 comparable scans generated using tumor image simulation software. Quantitative evaluations revealed considerable disagreement between the human raters in segmenting various tumor sub-regions (Dice scores in the range 74%–85%), illustrating the difficulty of this task. We found that different algorithms worked best for different sub-regions (reaching performance comparable to human inter-rater variability), but that no single algorithm ranked in the top for all sub-regions simultaneously. Fusing several good algorithms using a hierarchical majority vote yielded segmentations that consistently ranked above all individual algorithms, indicating remaining opportunities for further methodological improvements.

2.2 FULLY AUTOMATIC SEGMENTATION OF BRAIN TUMOR IMAGES USING SVM WITH HIERARCHICAL CONDITIONAL RANDOM FIELD REGULARIZATION

Delineating brain tumor boundaries from magnetic resonance images is an essential task for the analysis of brain cancer. We propose a fully automatic method for brain tissue segmentation, which combines Support Vector Machine classification using multispectral intensities and textures with subsequent hierarchical regularization based on Conditional Random Fields. The CRF regularization introduces spatial constraints to the powerful SVM classification, which assumes voxels to be independent from their neighbors. The approach first separates healthy and tumor tissue before both regions are subclassified into cerebrospinal fluid, white matter, gray matter and necrotic, active, edema region respectively in a novel hierarchical way. The hierarchical approach adds robustness and speed by allowing to apply different levels of regularization at different stages. The method is fast and tailored to standard clinical acquisition protocols. It was assessed on 10 multispectral patient datasets with results outperforming previous methods in terms of segmentation detail and computation times. This problem at hand as a classification task that maps each voxel to its corresponding label based on a multidimensional feature vector.

2.3 SEGMENTING BRAIN TUMORS USING PSEUDO-CONDITIONAL RANDOM FIELDS

Locating Brain tumor segmentation within MR (magnetic resonance) images is integral to the treatment of brain cancer. This segmentation task requires classifying each voxel as either tumor or nontumor, based on a description of that voxel. Unfortunately, standard classifiers, such as Logistic Regression (LR) and Support Vector Machines (SVM), typically have limited accuracy as they treat voxels as independent and identically distributed (iid). Approaches based on random fields, which are able to incorporate spatial constraints, have recently been applied to brain tumor segmentation with notable performance improvement over iid classifiers. However, previous random field systems involved computationally intractable formulations, which are typically solved using some approximation. Here, we present pseudo-conditional random fields (PCRFs), which achieve accuracy similar to other random fields variants, but are significantly more efficient. We formulate a PCRF as a regularized discriminative classifier that relaxes the classification decision for each voxel by considering the labels and features of neighboring pixels.

2.4 THE VISUAL HUMAN FACE SUPER-RESOLUTION RECONSTRUCTION ALGORITHM BASED ON IMPROVED DEEP RESIDUAL NETWORK

Deep learning is a hot method in face super-resolution reconstruction in recent years, but it needs to further improve the details of reconstructed images and speed up network training. This paper improves the deep residual network from two aspects of residual unit and network structure and proposes a face super-resolution reconstruction algorithm based on the improved model. We improve the network structure of the residual unit by connecting with a densely connected convolutional layer and removing the BN layer, thereby enhancing the information flow between the inner convolutional layers and eliminate the damage to the spatial information of the image by batch normalization processing. At the same time, we combine the output characteristics of each residual unit on the basis of the global residual structure, so the face feature information is more fully utilized and the model detail recovery ability is also improved. Experiments on FDDB and AFLW face datasets show that the proposed method has better performance in feature description and detail information reconstruction, and higher PSNR and SSIM than other methods.

2.5 CLINICALLY DRIVEN DESIGN OF MULTI-SCALE CANCER MODELS

The challenge of modelling cancer presents a major opportunity to improve our ability to reduce mortality from malignant neoplasms, improve treatments and meet the demands associated with the individualization of care needs. This is the central motivation behind the ContraCancrum project. By developing integrated multi-scale cancer models, ContraCancrum is expected to contribute to the advancement of in silico oncology through the optimization of cancer treatment in the patient-individualized context by simulating the response to various therapeutic regimens. The aim of the present paper is to describe a novel paradigm for designing clinically driven multi-scale cancer modelling by bringing together basic science and information technology modules. In addition, the integration of the multi-scale tumour modelling components has led to novel concepts of personalized clinical decision support in the context of predictive oncology, as is also discussed in the paper. Since clinical adaptation is an inelastic prerequisite, a long-term clinical adaptation procedure of the models has been initiated for two tumour types, namely non-small cell lung cancer and glioblastoma multiforme; its current status is briefly summarized.

2.6 BRAIN TUMOR TARGET VOLUME DETERMINATION FOR RADIATION TREATMENT PLANNING THROUGH AUTOMATED MRI SEGMENTATION

Two automated MRI tumor segmentation methods (supervised k-nearest neighbors [kNN] and automatic knowledge-guided [KG]) were evaluated for their potential as cyber colleagues to assess the effectiveness of two automated magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) segmentation methods in determining the gross tumor volume (GTV) of brain tumors for use in radiation therapy treatment planning. This required an initial determination of the accuracy and variability of radiation oncologists engaged in the manual definition of the GTV in MRI registered with computed tomography images for 11 glioma patients. Three sets of contours were defined for each of these patients by three radiation oncologists. These outlines were compared directly to establish inter- and intraoperator variability among the radiation oncologists. A novel, probabilistic measurement of accuracy was introduced to compare the level of agreement among the automated MRI segmentations. The accuracy was determined by comparing the volumes obtained by the automated segmentation methods with the weighted average volumes prepared by the radiation oncologists.

2.7 MULTIPARAMETRIC TISSUE CHARACTERIZATION OF BRAIN NEOPLASMS AND THEIR RECURRENCE USING PATTERN CLASSIFICATION OF MR IMAGES

Treatment of brain neoplasms can greatly benefit from better delineation of bulk neoplasm boundary and the extent and degree of more subtle neoplastic infiltration. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the primary imaging modality for evaluation before and after therapy, typically combining conventional sequences with more advanced techniques such as perfusion-weighted imaging and diffusion tensor imaging (DTI). The purpose of this study is to quantify the multiparametric imaging profile of neoplasms by integrating structural MRI and DTI via statistical image analysis methods to potentially capture complex and subtle tissue characteristics that are not obvious from any individual image or parameter. Five structural MRI sequences, namely, B_0 , diffusion-weighted images, fluid-attenuated inversion recovery, T1-weighted, and gadolinium-enhanced T1-weighted, and two scalar maps computed from DTI (ie, fractional anisotropy and apparent diffusion coefficient) are used to create an intensity-based tissue profile.

2.8 A DISCRIMINATIVE MODEL-CONSTRAINED GRAPH CUTS APPROACH TO FULLY AUTOMATED PEDIATRIC BRAIN TUMOR SEGMENTATION IN 3-D MRI

A fully automated approach to the segmentation of pediatric brain tumors in multi-spectral 3-D magnetic resonance images was presented here. It is a top-down segmentation approach based on Markov random field (MRF) model that combines probabilistic boosting trees (PBT) and lower-level segmentation via graph cuts. The PBT algorithm provides a strong discriminative observation model that classifies tumor appearance while a spatial prior takes into account the pair-wise homogeneity in terms of classification labels and multi-spectral voxel intensities. The discriminative model relies not only on observed local intensities but also on surrounding context for detecting candidate regions for pathology. A mathematically sound formulation for integrating the two approaches into a unified statistical framework is given. The proposed method is applied to the challenging task of detection and delineation of pediatric brain tumors. This segmentation task is characterized by a high non-uniformity of both the pathology and the surrounding non-pathologic brain tissue. A quantitative evaluation illustrates the robustness of the proposed method.

2.9 OPTIMAL SYMMETRIC MULTIMODAL TEMPLATES AND CONCATENATED RANDOM FORESTS FOR SUPERVISED BRAIN TUMOR SEGMENTATION (SIMPLIFIED) WITH ANTSR

Segmenting and quantifying gliomas from MRI is an important task for diagnosis, planning intervention, and for tracking tumor changes over time. However, this task is complicated by the lack of prior knowledge concerning tumor location, spatial extent, shape, possible displacement of normal tissue, and intensity signature. To accommodate such complications, a framework for supervised segmentation was introduced based on multiple modality intensity, geometry, and asymmetry feature sets. These features drive a supervised whole-brain and tumor segmentation approach based on random forest-derived probabilities. Performance gain can be achieved by generating probability maps from random forest models and using these maps for a refining Markov random field regularized probabilistic segmentation. This strategy allows us to interface the supervised learning capabilities of the random forest model with regularized probabilistic segmentation using the recently developed ANTsR package--a comprehensive statistical and visualization interface between the popular Advanced Normalization Tools (ANTs) and the R statistical project.

2.10 LINKS:LEARNING-BASED MULTI-SOURCE INTEGRATION FRAMEWORK FOR SEGMENTATION OF INFANT BRAIN IMAGES

Segmentation of infant brain MR images is challenging due to insufficient image quality, severe partial volume effect, and ongoing maturation and myelination processes. In the first year of life, the image contrast between white and gray matters of the infant brain undergoes dramatic changes. In particular, the image contrast is inverted around 6-8months of age, and the white and gray matter tissues are isointense in both T1- and T2-weighted MR images and thus exhibit the extremely low tissue contrast, which poses significant challenges for automated segmentation. Most previous studies used multi-atlas label fusion strategy, which has the limitation of equally treating the different available image modalities and is often computationally expensive. A novel learning-based multi-source integration framework is proposed for segmentation of infant brain images. Specifically, we employ the random forest technique to effectively integrate features from multi-source images together for tissue segmentation. Here, the multi-source images include initially only the multi-modality (T1, T2 and FA) images and later also the iteratively estimated and refined tissue probability maps of gray matter, white matter, and cerebrospinal fluid.

CHAPTER 3

3.1 THEORITICAL BACKGROUND

The history of brain tumor diagnosis from antiquity to the present and, indirectly, the history of neuroradiology. Imaging of the brain has from the beginning held an enormous interest because of the inherent difficulty of this endeavor due to the presence of the skull. Because of this, most techniques when newly developed have always been used in neuroradiology and, although some have proved to be inappropriate for this purpose, many were easily incorporated into the specialty. The first major advance in modern neuroimaging was contrast agent-enhanced computed tomography, which permitted accurate anatomic localization of brain tumors and, by virtue of contrast enhancement, malignant ones. The most important advances in neuroimaging occurred with the development of magnetic resonance imaging and diffusion-weighted sequences that allowed an indirect estimation of tumor cellularity; this was further refined by the development of perfusion and permeability mapping. From its beginnings with indirect and purely anatomic imaging techniques, neuroradiology now uses a combination of anatomic and physiologic techniques that will play a critical role in biologic tumor imaging and radiologic genomics. In antiquity, brain tumors resulted in death and were preceded by longstanding symptoms of headaches, seizures, and coma. Physicians recognized that these symptoms were caused by increased intracranial pressure and

developed skull trepanation to relieve it. Many Byzantine physicians do not mention brain tumors in their treatises but left clear instructions regarding trepanation to alleviate intracranial pressure. Since many neurosurgical techniques were perfected at a time of a war, it should come as no surprise that the Incas, a military state, not only used trepanation but were proficient in performing craniotomies with exquisite knowledge of anatomy, preserving vital structures such as veins and implanting prosthetic materials with relatively low rates of infection. It seems that most Inca surgery was performed for trauma, and no documentation of tumor resections exists. Although other tumors disappear as the accompanying brain lyses and disintegrates after death, evidence of meningioma remains in ancient skulls. Hyperostosis, commonly produced by meningioma, has been found in Neolithic, Egyptian, and South American skulls. However, there is no evidence that these tumors were ever treated. The presence of clinically palpable external hyperostosis was used to localize the first documented resected meningioma in 1881. Also at that time, emulsion-coated glass plates were used by radiologists to help diagnose brain tumors. Intracranial calcifications, which can indicate tumors such as oligodendroglioma, meningioma, and pituitary tumor, are easily seen in images in 1927. Cranial nerve VIII schwannomas were diagnosed by demonstrating expanded internal auditory canals on oblique skull radiographs, optic nerve gliomas could be inferred by enlargement of the optic canals, and cranial nerve tumors were suggested by expansion of their corresponding outlet foramina.

3.2 CONCEPT

Improved fuzzy C means (TKFCM) algorithm for detecting human brain tumors in a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) image. The template-based K-means algorithm is used to initialize segmentation significantly through the perfect selection of a template, based on gray-level intensity of image; secondly, the updated membership is determined by the distances from cluster centroid to cluster data points using the fuzzy C-means (FCM) algorithm while it contacts its best result, and finally, the improved FCM clustering algorithm is used for detecting tumor position by updating membership function that is obtained based on the different features of tumor image including Contrast, Energy, Dissimilarity, Homogeneity, Entropy, and Correlation. Simulation results show that the proposed algorithm achieves better detection of abnormal and normal tissues in the human brain under small detachment of gray-level intensity. In addition, this algorithm detects human brain tumors within a very short time—in seconds compared to minutes with other algorithms. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) scans are used most often to look for brain diseases. These scans will almost always show a brain tumor, if one is present. A Brain Tumor MRI is Highly Accurate. According to cancer.net, an MRI is the most effective diagnostic tool for detecting a brain tumor in most cases.

3.3 METHODOLOGIES

3.3.1 PRE PROCESSING

Preprocessing refers to all the transformations on the raw data before it is fed to the machine learning or deep learning algorithm. For instance, training a convolutional neural network on raw images will probably lead to bad classification performances. Image preprocessing are the steps taken to format images before they are used by model training and inference. This includes, but is not limited to, resizing, orienting, and color corrections. ... Thus, a transformation that could be an augmentation in some situations may best be a preprocessing step in others.

FIGURE 3.3.1 WORK FLOW OF PRE PROCESSING

3.3.1.1 MEDIAN FILTERING

Like lowpass filtering, median filtering smooths the image and is thus useful in reducing noise. Unlike lowpass filtering, median filtering can preserve discontinuities in a step function and can smooth a few pixels whose values differ significantly from their surroundings without affecting the other pixels. The median filter is the filtering technique used for noise removal from images and signals. Median filter is very crucial in the image processing field as it is well known for the preservation of edges during noise removal. The median filter is the filtering technique

used for noise removal from images and signals. Median filter is very crucial in the image processing field as it is well known for the preservation of edges during noise removal.

3.3.1.2 PADDING IN CONVOLUTION LAYERS:

A simple CNN gives results For a grayscale image of size $(n \times n)$ with $(f \times f)$ filter/kernel size is $(n - f + 1) \times (n - f + 1)$. For example in any convolution operation with a (8×8) image and (3×3) filter the output image size will be (6×6) . So this happens every time when processing images, the output of the layers is shrunk in comparison to the input. Also, the filters we are using do not focus on the corners every time when it moves on the pixels. For example, A simple CNN gives results For a grayscale image of size $(n \times n)$ with $(f \times f)$ filter/kernel size is $(n - f + 1) \times (n - f + 1)$. For example in any convolution operation with a (8×8) image and (3×3) filter the output image size will be (6×6) . So this happens every time when processing images, the output of the layers is shrunk in comparison to the input. Also, the filters we are using do not focus on the corners every time when it moves on the pixels.

There are three types of padding:

- Same padding
- Causal padding
- Valid padding

We use this padding with convolutional layers which basically means every layer is using the learnt part of the previous layer and again the learnt part of the will go to the next layer and this is how it all works.

For example,

3.3.2 PADDING IN CONVOLUTION LAYER

The above image is an example of the movement of a filter of size (3 x 3) on an image of size (6 x 6). We can clearly see that a corner pixel A is coming under the filter in only one movement where b is coming in three movements and c is coming under 9 movements. It basically shows that the model will work with pixel C very fine and it

will misinterpret pixel A. This will cause the loss of information available in the corners and also the output from the layers is reduced and reduced information will create confusion for the next layers. This problem of the model can be reduced by the padding layers.

USE OF PADDING:

3.3.3 USAGE OF ZERO PADDING MODEL

In the above image, we added the padding layer(grey color rows and columns) on an image and this is how it saves the size of the image matrix from reducing the size. A model architecture consisting of causal padding with a kernel size of four can be represented as:

3.3.4 ARCHITECTURE OF ZERO PADDING WITH KERNEL

And a whole time series model architecture with a fully connected layer and causal padding can be like:

3.3.5 PADDING MODEL ARCHITECTURE WITH FULLY CONNECTED LAYER

3.3.2 SEGMENTATION:

Segmentation is an important stage of the image recognition system, because it extracts the objects of our interest, for further processing such as description or recognition. ... Segmentation techniques are used to isolate the desired object from the image in order to perform analysis of the object.

3.3.2.1 THRESHOLDING:

In image segmentation each pixel in image is labeled to different class. This pixel labeling task is also called as dense prediction. ... We can differentiate objects of the same type using instance segmentation. CNN is used very frequently for segmenting the image in pattern recognition and object identification.

Using thresholding and morphological operations efficient brain tumor segmentation is carried out. ... To detect the brain tumor, scanned MRI images are given as the input. The work involved here helps in medical field to detect tumor and its features helps in giving the treatment plan to the patient.

3.3.3 FEATURE EXTRACTION:

3.3.3.1 GREY LEVEL CO-OCCURENCE MATRIX:

Texture Analysis Using the **Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM)** ... The GLCM functions characterize the texture of an image by calculating how often pairs of pixel with specific values and in a specified spatial relationship occur in an image, creating a GLCM, and then extracting statistical measures from this matrix. Level Cooccurrence Matrix (GLCM) method is a way of extracting second order statistical texture features. The approach has been used in a number of applications, Third and higher order textures consider the relationships among three or more pixels. ... Thus, the number of gray levels is often reduced. The function creates a gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) by calculating how often a pixel with the intensity (gray-level) value i occurs in a specific spatial relationship to a pixel with the value j . By default, the spatial relationship is defined as the pixel of interest and the pixel to its

immediate right (horizontally adjacent), but you can specify other spatial relationships between the two pixels. Each element (i,j) in the resultant glcm is simply the sum of the number of times that the pixel with value i occurred in the specified spatial relationship to a pixel with value j in the input image.

The number of gray levels in the image determines the size of the GLCM. By default, `graycomatrix` uses scaling to reduce the number of intensity values in an image to eight, but you can use the `NumLevels` and the `GrayLimits` parameters to control this scaling of gray levels. See the `graycomatrix` reference page for more information. The gray-level co-occurrence matrix can reveal certain properties about the spatial distribution of the gray levels in the texture image. For example, if most of the entries in the GLCM are concentrated along the diagonal, the texture is coarse with respect to the specified offset. You can also derive several statistical measures from the GLCM. See `Derive Statistics from GLCM` and `Plot Correlation` for more information. To illustrate, the following figure shows how `graycomatrix` calculates the first three values in a GLCM. In the output GLCM, element $(1,1)$ contains the value 1 because there is only one instance in the input image where two horizontally adjacent pixels have the values 1 and 1, respectively. `glcm(1,2)` contains the value 2 because there are two instances where two horizontally adjacent pixels have the values 1 and 2. Element $(1,3)$ in the GLCM has the value 0 because there are no instances of two horizontally adjacent pixels with the values 1 and 3. `graycomatrix` continues processing the input image, scanning the image for other pixel pairs (i,j) and recording the sums in the corresponding elements of the GLCM.

3.3.6 STRUCTURE OF GLCM

3.3.3.1.1 REGION GROWING TECHNIQUE:

If the adjacent pixels abide by the predefined rules, then that pixel is added to the region of the seed pixel and the following process continues till there is no similarity left. This method follows the bottom-up approach.

Seeded region growing (SRG) is a fast, effective and robust method for image segmentation. It begins with placing a set of seeds in the image to be segmented, where each seed could be a single pixel or a set of connected pixels. Then SRG grows these seeds into regions by successively adding neighboring pixels to them.

3.3.3.1.2 BOUNDARY EXTRACTION METHOD:

Extracting the boundary is the important process to gain the **information** and understand the feature of an image. Boundary extraction is the first process in preprocessing in order to present the features of the image. This process can help the researcher to gain the data from the image. Extracting the boundary is the important process to gain the information and understand the feature of an image. Boundary

extraction is the first process in preprocessing in order to present the features of the image. This process can help the researcher to gain the data from the image. There are a lot of proposed methods in detecting the boundary of the image. Yahya (2009) introduced a spatial filter in order to extract the boundary. In the initial process, the 7 by 7 average spatial filter is used to smooth out the digital image. In the next process, thresholding is applied to convert the digital image into binary image. The boundary image is obtained from the binary image by using the method in mathematical morphology. Every third pixels of the boundary image is chose to get a final boundary image. This process is suitable for the boundary image that has the same distance for every pixel.

3.3.4 CLUSTERING

Clustering is a powerful technique that has been reached in image segmentation. The cluster analysis is to partition an image data set into a number of disjoint groups or clusters. The clustering methods such as k means, improved k mean, fuzzy c mean (FCM) and improved fuzzy c mean algorithm (IFCM) have been proposed. Clustering itself can be categorized into two types viz. Hard Clustering and Soft Clustering. In hard clustering, one data point can belong to one cluster only. But in soft clustering, the output provided is a probability likelihood of a data point belonging to each of the pre-defined numbers of clusters.

HARD CLUSTERING:

In hard clustering, each data point is clustered or grouped to any one cluster. For each data point, it may either completely belong to a cluster or not. As observed in the above diagram, the data points are divided into two clusters, each point belonging to either of the two clusters.

Example : K-Means Clustering is a hard clustering algorithm. It clusters data points into k-clusters.

SOFT CLUSTERING:

In soft clustering, instead of putting each data points into separate clusters, a probability of that point to be in that cluster assigned. In soft clustering or fuzzy clustering, each data point can belong to multiple clusters along with its probability score or likelihood. One of the widely used soft clustering algorithms is the Fuzzy C-means clustering (FCM) Algorithm.

3.3.4.1 FUZZY C-MEANS CLUSTERING

Fuzzy C-Means clustering is a soft clustering approach, where each data point is assigned a likelihood or probability score to belong to that cluster. The step-wise approach of the Fuzzy c-means clustering algorithm is:

- (i) Fix the value of c (number of clusters), and select a value of m (generally $1.25 < m < 2$), and initialize partition matrix U .

$$PartitionMatrix = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

- Calculate cluster centers (centroid).

$$V_{ij} = \left(\sum_1^n (\gamma_{ik}^m * x_k) / \sum_1^n \gamma_{ik}^m \right)$$

- Update Partition Matrix

$$\gamma = \sum_1^n \left(d_{ki}^2 / d_{kj}^2 \right)^{1/m-1}]^{-1}$$

The above steps can be repeated until convergence.

3.3.5 CNN USING DEEP LEARNING:

Technically, deep learning CNN models **to train and test**, each input image will pass it through a series of convolution layers with filters (Kernels), Pooling, fully connected layers (FC) and apply Softmax function to classify an object with probabilistic values between 0 and 1. A typical neural network will have an input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer. CNNs are inspired by the architecture of the brain. Just like a neuron in the brain processes and transmits information throughout the body, artificial neurons or nodes in CNNs take inputs, processes them and sends the result as output. The image is fed as input. The input layer accepts the image pixels as input in the form of arrays. In CNNs, there could be multiple hidden layers, which perform feature extraction from the image by doing calculations. This could include convolution, pooling, rectified linear units, and fully connected layers. Convolution is the first layer that does feature extraction from an input image. The fully connected layer classifies the object and identifies it in the output layer. “CNNs are feedforward networks in that information flow takes place in one direction only,

from their inputs to their outputs. The visual cortex in the brain, consisting of alternating layers of simple and complex cells, motivates their architecture. CNN architectures come in several variations; however, in general, they consist of convolutional and pooling (or subsampling) layers, which are grouped into modules.

3.3.7 ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK

3.4 DESIGN

FIG 3.4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The neural network architecture of the convolutional neural network process is shown in the below diagram.

FIGURE 3.4.2 NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

Neural Networks are complex structures made of artificial neurons that can take in multiple inputs to produce a single output. This is the primary job of a Neural Network – to transform input into a meaningful output. Usually, a Neural Network consists of an input and output layer with one or multiple hidden layers within. In a Neural Network, all the neurons influence each other, and hence, they are all connected. The network can acknowledge and observe every aspect of the dataset at hand and how the different parts of data may or may not relate to each other.

3.5 MODELING

Unified Modeling Language is a general purpose modelling language. The main aim of UML is to define a standard way to visualize the way a system has been designed. It is quite similar to blueprints used in other fields of engineering. UML is not a programming language, it is rather a visual language. We use UML diagrams to portray the behavior and structure of a system. UML helps software engineers, businessmen and system architects with modelling, design and analysis.

A UML diagram is a diagram based on the UML (Unified Modeling Language) with the purpose of visually representing a system along with its main actors, roles, actions, artifacts or classes, in order to better understand, alter, maintain, or document information about the system. From the many diagrams proposed by UML, class diagrams and sequence diagrams are still widely used, certainly followed by state diagrams: they can easily be used on white boards to elaborate and discuss design before jumping in the code. UML never died because it never lived. It was always a zombie kept alive by Rational Software doing a really good job of generating enough hype, and market share, to sell to IBM for \$3.1 billion.

3.5.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM

FIG 3.4.3 USE CASE DIAGRAM

3.5.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

FIG 3.4.4 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

3.5.3 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

FIG 3.4.5 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

3.5.4 STATECHART DIAGRAM

FIG 3.4.6 STATECHART DIAGRAM

3.5.5 CLASS DIAGRAM

FIG 3.4.7 CLASS DIAGRAM

3.5.6 COLLABORATION DIAGRAM

FIG 3.4.8 COLLABORATION DIAGRAM

CHAPTER 4

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The requirement specification is a technical specification of requirements of the software products. It is the first step in the requirement analysis process, it lists the requirements of a particular software system include functional, performance. The requirements also provide usage scenario from the user, an operational and an administrative perspective. The purpose of software requirements specification is to provide a detailed overview of the software project, its parameter and goals. This describes the project target audience and its user interface, hardware and software requirements.

4.1.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENT

The most common set of requirements defined by any operating system or software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware, A hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a hardware compatibility list (HCL), especially in case of operating systems. An HCL lists tested, compatible, and sometimes incompatible hardware devices for a particular operating system or application. The following sub-sections discuss the various aspects of hardware requirements.

- Operating System : Windows 10
- Memory : 64 GB

- Speed: 1.6GHz

4.1.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT

Software requirements deal with defining software resource requirements and prerequisites that need to be installed on a computer to provide optimal functioning of an application. These requirements or prerequisites are generally not included in the software installation package and need to be installed separately before the software is installed.

- GUI :Anaconda
- Tool: Jupyter Notebook
- Front End: Python
- Library: Tensor flow
- Library: Keras
- Library: OpenCV
- Engine: Docker

4.2 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

4.2.1 PYTHON

Python is an interpreted high-level general-purpose programming language. Its design philosophy emphasizes code readability with its use of significant indentation. Its language constructs as well as its object-oriented approach aim to help programmers write clear, logical code for small and large-scale projects. Python is dynamically-typed and garbage-collected. It supports multiple programming

paradigms, including structured (particularly, procedural), object-oriented and functional programming. It is often described as a "batteries included" language due to its comprehensive standard library. Guido van Rossum began working on Python in the late 1980s, as a successor to the ABC programming language, and first released it in 1991 as Python 0.9.0. Python 2.0 was released in 2000 and introduced new features, such as list comprehensions and a cycle-detecting garbage collection system (in addition to reference counting). Python 3.0 was released in 2008 and was a major revision of the language that is not completely backward-compatible. Python 2 was discontinued with version 2.7.18 in 2020. Python consistently ranks as one of the most popular programming languages.

4.2.2 PYTHON PLATFORM

Python defines an in-built module platform that provides system information. The Platform module is used to retrieve as much possible information about the platform on which the program is being currently executed. Now by platform info, it means information about the device, it's OS, node, OS version, Python version, etc. This module plays a crucial role when you want to check whether your program is compatible with the python version installed on a particular system or whether the hardware specifications meet the requirements of your program. This module already exists in the python library and does not require any installation using pip.

4.2.3 ANACONDA

Anaconda is a distribution of the Python and R programming languages for scientific computing (data science, machine learning applications, large-scale data processing, predictive analytics, etc.), that aims to simplify package management and deployment. The distribution includes data-science packages suitable for Windows, Linux, and macOS. It is developed and maintained by Anaconda, Inc., which was founded by Peter Wang and Travis Oliphant in 2012. As an Anaconda, Inc. product, it is also known as Anaconda Distribution or Anaconda Individual Edition, while other products from the company are Anaconda Team Edition and Anaconda Enterprise Edition, both of which are not free. Package versions in Anaconda are managed by the package management system conda. This package manager was spun out as a separate open-source package as it ended up being useful on its own and for things other than Python. There is also a small, bootstrap version of Anaconda called Miniconda, which includes only conda, Python, the packages they depend on, and a small number of other packages.

4.2.4 JUPYTER NOTEBOOK

The Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that allows data scientists to create and share documents that integrate live code, equations, computational output, visualizations, and other multimedia resources, along with explanatory text in a single document. The Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that allows data scientists to create and share documents that integrate live code, equations, computational output, visualizations, and other multimedia resources, along with explanatory text in a single document. Jupyter Notebooks can be used for all sorts of data science tasks including data cleaning and transformation, numerical

simulation, exploratory data analysis, data visualization, statistical modeling, machine learning, deep learning, and much more. A Jupyter Notebook provides you with an easy-to-use, interactive data science environment that doesn't only work as an integrated development environment (IDE), but also as a presentation or educational tool. Jupyter is a way of working with Python inside a virtual "notebook" and is growing in popularity with data scientists in large part due to its flexibility. It gives you a way to combine code, images, plots, comments, etc., in alignment with the step of the "data science process." Further, it is a form of interactive computing, an environment in which users execute code, see what happens, modify, and repeat in a kind of iterative conversation between the data scientist and data.

4.2.5 TENSORFLOW

TensorFlow is a free and open-source software library for machine learning and artificial intelligence. It can be used across a range of tasks but has a particular focus on training and inference of deep neural networks. It has various platforms in Linux, Windows, MacOS, Ubuntu, Android, JavaScript etc.,. It is an open source artificial intelligence library, using data flow graphs to build models. It allows developers to create large-scale neural networks with many layers. TensorFlow is mainly used for: Classification, Perception, Understanding, Discovering, Prediction and Creation.

4.2.6 KERAS

Keras is a high-level, deep learning API developed by Google for implementing neural networks. It is written in Python and is used to make the

implementation of neural networks easy. It is an open-source software library that provides a Python interface for artificial neural networks and also supports multiple backend neural network computation. Keras acts as an interface for the TensorFlow library. Up until version 2.3, Keras supported multiple backends, including TensorFlow, Microsoft Cognitive Toolkit, Theano, and PlaidML.

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM TESTING

5.1 TESTING OBJECTIVES

Software testing is a crucial element in the software development life cycle (SDLC), which can help software engineers save time & money of organizations by finding errors and defects during the early stages of software development. With the assistance of this process one can examine various components associated with the application and guarantee their appropriateness. The goals and objectives of software testing are numerous, which when achieved help developers build a defect-less and error free software and application that has exceptional performance, quality, effectiveness, security, among other things. Though the objective of testing can vary from company to company and project to project, there are some goals that are similar for all. The benefits and advantages offered by software testing are innumerable. It helps software developers and programmers in verifying and validating various components of the software as well as in detecting bugs and defects. Moreover, it helps them deliver a software product that has remarkable quality and innovative features.

Type of Testing

There are two types of testing according their behaviors. They are:

1. Unconventional Testing
2. Conventional Testing

Unconventional Testing

Unconventional testing is a process of verification which is done by software quality assurance team. It is a prevention technique which is performing from begging to ending of the project development. In this process SQA team verifies project development activities and insuring that developing project is fulfilling the requirement of the client or not.

Conventional Testing

Conventional testing is a process of finding the bugs and validating the project. Testing team involves in this testing process and validating that developed project is according to client requirement or not. This process is a correction technique where testing team bugs and reporting to the development team for correction on developed project built.

5.2 TEST CASE DESIGN

5.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit tests are typically automated tests written and run by software developers to ensure that a section of an application (known as the "unit") meets its design and behaves as intended. In procedural programming, a unit could be an entire module, but it is more commonly an individual function or procedure. In object-oriented programming, a unit is often an entire interface, such as a class, or an individual method. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unit_testing - cite note-3 By writing tests first for the smallest testable units, then the compound behaviors between those, one can build up comprehensive tests for complex applications. To isolate issues that may

arise, each test case should be tested independently. Substitutes such as method stubs, mock objects, fakes, and test harnesses can be used to assist testing a module in isolation.

5.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional testing is a quality assurance (QA) process and a type of black-box testing that bases its test cases on the specifications of the software component under test. Functions are tested by feeding them input and examining the output, and internal program structure is rarely considered (unlike white-box testing). Functional testing is conducted to evaluate the compliance of a system or component with specified functional requirements. Functional testing usually describes what the system does.

Since functional testing is a type of black-box testing, the software's functionality can be tested without knowing the internal workings of the software. This means that testers do not need to know programming languages or how the software has been implemented. This, in turn, could lead to reduced developer bias (or confirmation bias) in testing since the tester has not been involved in the software's development. Functional testing does not imply that you are testing a function (method) of your module or class. Functional testing tests a slice of functionality of the whole system.

5.2.3 System Testing

System testing is testing conducted on a complete integrated system to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements. System testing takes, as its

input, all of the integrated components that have passed integration testing. The purpose of integration testing is to detect any inconsistencies between the units that are integrated together. System testing seeks to detect defects both within the "inter-assemblages" and also within the system as a whole. The actual result is the behavior produced or observed when a component or system is tested.

5.2.4 Acceptance Testing

Acceptance testing is a test conducted to determine if the requirements of specification or contract are met. It may involve chemical tests, physical tests, or performance tests. In systems engineering, it may involve black-box testing performed on a system .

CHAPTER 6

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main application of brain tumour segmentation in the clinical sphere is quantitative image analysis. Brain tumours have traditionally been analysed qualitatively through inspection, and this have given rise to an elaborate feature lexicon summarised by projects such as Visually AcceSAbLe Rembrandt Images (VASARI) [32]. Radiomics is a field focused on quantitative feature analysis. This field is focused on extracting voxel and volume features of the tumour habitat and predicting clinical outcomes such as survival. It has been used to grade tumours, evaluate response to therapy and predict genetic status of GBM—for example, isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH) status in GBM, which is of clinical significance since negative status (or ‘wildtype’) implies a more aggressive tumour [33]. Segmentation and the processes involved in extraction can be translated into meaningful analysis in radiomics. Radiomic features such as shape, texture, intensity, and patterns of the microvasculature have been extensively studied in GBM .Shape and texture represent the most extensively studied radiomic features. Filtration matrices that are applied during the convolution of images during the segmentation processes can subsequently be used to predict clinical outcomes such as survival. For example, in a study by Sanghani et al. [35], 2200 shape, volumetric, and texture features were extracted from 163 patients. Using kernels for each feature, i.e. shape, texture, and volume, prediction

of overall survival was sorted into groups with short (< 10 months), medium (10–15 months), and long (> 15 months) term survival with 88.95% accuracy. In the same study, prediction of short (< 400 days) and long (> 400 days) was shown to have a higher accuracy of 98.7%. This demonstrates the novelty of radiomics in predicting clinical outcomes and the importance of translating segmentation algorithms into radiology. Deep learning has an important role in the automation of quantitative image analysis. The dataset is trained using feature extractions on a training dataset which necessitates the need for feeding fixed parameters. Machinelearning through multiple iterations can provide more accurate results than standard voxel-based manipulation methods. Survival prediction for classification into short, medium and long term survival has shown to have a moderate accuracy of up to 57.8% using ensemble learning (combination of multiple machine learning algorithms).

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION AND ADVANCED WORK SCHEDULE

Convolutional neural networks remain a growing area of research in automated tumour segmentation. It is important for radiologists to have a working knowledge of convolutional neural networks so that they are well positioned to deploy these tools in future clinical practice. A basic overview is provided in this paper that allows the reader to be well-informed in the world of automated segmentation. Clinical applicability to GBM is highly relevant as brain tumour segmentation from normal parenchyma is the first step in the utilisation of quantitative image feature analysis such as radiomics for prognostication, and treatment planning. Through the further development of segmentation techniques in brain tumours, this could be applied to other areas of radiology. Convolutional neural networks represent a growing field that will likely help radiologists provide more accurate care for their patients. Further work is needed in this area to investigate the highest hybrid median filtering of survival, and this can be achieved by translation of segmentation features extraction and modelling into radiomics.

APPENDICES

A. SAMPLE CODE

```
import tensorflow as tf\n",\n\n"from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D, Input, ZeroPadding2D,\nBatchNormalization, Activation, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense\n",\n\n"from tensorflow.keras.models import Model, load_model\n",\n\n"from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import TensorBoard, ModelCheckpoint\n",\n\n"from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split\n",\n\n"from sklearn.metrics import f1_score\n",\n\n"from sklearn.utils import shuffle\n",\n\n"import cv2\n",\n\n"import imutils\n",\n\n"import numpy as np\n",\n\n"import matplotlib.pyplot as plt\n",\n\n"import time\n",\n\n"from os import listdir\n",\n\n"\n",\n\n"%matplotlib inline"\n\n]\n\n},
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"## Data Preparation & Preprocessing"
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"def crop_brain_contour(image, plot=False):\n",
" \n",
" #import imutils\n",
" #import cv2\n",

```

```

" #from matplotlib import pyplot as plt\n",
" \n",
" # Convert the image to grayscale, and blur it slightly\n",
" gray = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)\n",
" gray = cv2.GaussianBlur(gray, (5, 5), 0)\n",
"\n",
" # Threshold the image, then perform a series of erosions +\n",
" # dilations to remove any small regions of noise\n",
" thresh = cv2.threshold(gray, 45, 255, cv2.THRESH_BINARY)[1]\n",
" thresh = cv2.erode(thresh, None, iterations=2)\n",
" thresh = cv2.dilate(thresh, None, iterations=2)\n",
"\n",
" # Find contours in thresholded image, then grab the largest one\n",
"     cnts = cv2.findContours(thresh.copy(), cv2.RETR_EXTERNAL,
cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)\n",
"     cnts = imutils.grab_contours(cnts)\n",
"     c = max(cnts, key=cv2.contourArea)\n",
" \n",
"\n",
" # Find the extreme points\n",
"     extLeft = tuple(c[c[:, :, 0].argmin()][0])\n",
"     extRight = tuple(c[c[:, :, 0].argmax()][0])\n",
"     extTop = tuple(c[c[:, :, 1].argmin()][0])

```

```

" extBot = tuple(c[c[:, :, 1].argmax()][0])\n",
" \n",
" # crop new image out of the original image using the four extreme points (left,
right, top, bottom)\n",
" new_image = image[extTop[1]:extBot[1], extLeft[0]:extRight[0]] \n",
"\n",
" if plot:\n",
"     plt.figure()\n",
"\n",
"     plt.subplot(1, 2, 1)\n",
"     plt.imshow(image)\n",
"     \n",
"     plt.tick_params(axis='both', which='both', \n",
"                     top=False, bottom=False, left=False, right=False,\n",
" labelbottom=False, labeltop=False, labelleft=False, labelright=False)\n",
"     \n",
"     plt.title('Original Image')\n",
"     \n",
"     plt.subplot(1, 2, 2)\n",
"     plt.imshow(new_image)\n",
"\n",
"     plt.tick_params(axis='both', which='both', \n",
"                     top=False, bottom=False, left=False, right=False,\n",

```

```

"                labelbottom=False, labeltop=False, labelleft=False,
labelright=False)\n",
"\n",
"    plt.title('Cropped Image')\n",
"    \n",
"    plt.show()\n",
"    \n",
"    return new_image"
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"ex_new_img = crop_brain_contour(ex_img, True)"
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"def load_data(dir_list, image_size):\n",
"    \"\"\"\n",
"    Read images, resize and normalize them. \n",
"    Arguments:\n",
"        dir_list: list of strings representing file directories.\n",
"    Returns:\n",
"        X: A numpy array with shape = (#_examples, image_width, image_height,
#_channels)\n",
"        y: A numpy array with shape = (#_examples, 1)\n",
"    \"\"\"\n",
"\n",
"    # load all images in a directory\n",
"    X = []\n",
"    y = []

```

```

" image_width, image_height = image_size\n",
" \n",
" for directory in dir_list:\n",
"     for filename in listdir(directory):\n",
"         # load the image\n",
"         image = cv2.imread(directory + '\\\\' + filename)\n",
"         # crop the brain and ignore the unnecessary rest part of the image\n",
"         image = crop_brain_contour(image, plot=False)\n",
"         # resize image\n",
"             image = cv2.resize(image, dsize=(image_width, image_height),
interpolation=cv2.INTER_CUBIC)\n",
"         # normalize values\n",
"         image = image / 255.\n",
"         # convert image to numpy array and append it to X\n",
"         X.append(image)\n",
"         # append a value of 1 to the target array if the image\n",
"         # is in the folder named 'yes', otherwise append 0.\n",
"         if directory[-3:] == 'yes':\n",
"             y.append([1])\n",
"         else:\n",
"             y.append([0])\n",
"         \n",
" X = np.array(X)\n",

```

```
" y = np.array(y)\n",  
" \n",  
" # Shuffle the data\n",  
" X, y = shuffle(X, y)\n",  
" \n",  
" print(f'Number of examples is: {len(X)}')\n",  
" print(f'X shape is: {X.shape}')\n",  
" print(f'y shape is: {y.shape}')\n",  
" \n",  
" return X, y"
```

```
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  {
```

```
  {
```

```

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"X shape is: (2065, 240, 240, 3)\n",
"y shape is: (2065, 1)\n"
]
},
"source": [
"augmented_path = 'augmented data/\n",
"\n",
"# augmented data (yes and no) contains both the original and the new generated
examples\n",
"augmented_yes = augmented_path + 'yes' \n",
"augmented_no = augmented_path + 'no'\n",
"\n",
"IMG_WIDTH, IMG_HEIGHT = (240, 240)\n",
"\n",
"X, y = load_data([augmented_yes, augmented_no], (IMG_WIDTH,
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"def plot_sample_images(X, y, n=50):\n",
"    \"\"\"\n",

```

```

" Plots n sample images for both values of y (labels).\n",
" Arguments:\n",
"     X: A numpy array with shape = (#_examples, image_width, image_height,
#_channels)\n",
"     y: A numpy array with shape = (#_examples, 1)\n",
"     \"\"\"\n",
"     \n",
"     for label in [0,1]:\n",
"         # grab the first n images with the corresponding y values equal to label\n",
"         images = X[np.argwhere(y == label)]\n",
"         n_images = images[:n]\n",
"         \n",
"         columns_n = 10\n",
"         rows_n = int(n/ columns_n)\n",
"\n",
"         plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))\n",
"         \n",
"         i = 1 # current plot     \n",
"         for image in n_images:\n",
"             plt.subplot(rows_n, columns_n, i)\n",
"             plt.imshow(image[0])\n",
"             \n",
"             # remove ticks\n",

```

```

"         plt.tick_params(axis='both', which='both', \n",
"             top=False, bottom=False, left=False, right=False,\n",
"                 labelbottom=False, labeltop=False, labelleft=False,
labelright=False)\n",
"         \n",
"         i += 1\n",
"     \n",
"     label_to_str = lambda label: \"Yes\" if label == 1 else \"No\"\n",
"     plt.suptitle(f\"Brain Tumor: {label_to_str(label)}\")\n",
"     plt.show()
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"0.88 f1 score on the test set.<br>\n",
"These results are very good considering that the data is balanced."
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"| ----- | ----- | ----- \n",

```

```
"| Accuracy | 91%      | 89%   |\n",  
"| F1 score | 0.91      | 0.88  |"  
  
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B. SCREENSHOT OF OUTPUT

C. REFERENCE

- [1] P. Peng, K. Lekadir, A. Gooya, L. Shao, S. E. Petersen, and A. F. Frangi, "A review of heart chamber segmentation for structural and functional analysis using cardiac magnetic resonance imaging," *MAGMA*, vol. 29, pp. 155-95, Dec 2021.
- [2] Menze BH, Jakab A, Bauer S, Kalpathy-Cramer J, Farahani K, Kirby J, et al., "The Multimodal Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Benchmark (BRATS)," *Medical Imaging, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 34, pp. 1993-2024, Apr 4 2021.
- [3] M. Prastawa, E. Bullitt, S. Ho, and G. Gerig, "A brain tumor segmentation framework based on outlier detection," *Med Image Anal.*, vol. 8, pp. 275-283, 2021.
- [4] . Bauer, L.-P. Nolte, and M. Reyes, "Fully automatic segmentation of brain tumor images using support vector machine classification in combination with hierarchical conditional random field regularization," *MICCAI*, vol. 6893, pp. 354-361, 2020.
- [5] Nicholas J. Tustison, K. L. Shrinidhi, MaxWintermark, Christopher R. Durst, Benjamin M. Kandel, James C. Gee, et al., "Optimal Symmetric Multimodal Templates and Concatenated Random Forests for Supervised Brain Tumor

Segmentation (Simplified) with ANTsR," *Neuroinformatics*, vol. 13, pp. 209-25, Apr 2020.

[6] L. Wang, Y. Gao, F. Shi, G. Li, J. Gilmore, W. Lin, et al., "LINKS:learning-based multi-source Integration framework for Segmentation of infant brain images," *Neuroimage*, vol. 108, pp. 160-72, Mar 2020.

[7] D. Zikic, B. Glocker, and A. Criminisi, "Encoding atlases by randomized classification forests for efficient multi-atlas label propagation," *Med Image Anal*, vol. 18, pp. 1262-1273, 2019.

[8] P. Kontschieder, M. Fiterau, A. Criminisi, and S. R. Bulç, "Deep Neural Decision Forests," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2019, pp. 1467-1475.

[9] M. Kass, A. Witkin, and D. Terzopoulos, "Snakes: Active Contour Models," *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 1, pp. 321-331, 2019.

[10] P. Peng, K. Lekadir, A. Gooya, L. Shao, S. E. Petersen, and A. F. Frangi, "A review of heart chamber segmentation for structural and functional analysis using cardiac magnetic resonance imaging," *MAGMA*, vol. 29, pp. 155-95, Apr 2019.

[11] A. Sciences, M. Scientific, and P. Corp, 'Brain Tumor Detection and Classification Using Deep Learning Classifier on MRI Images V . P . Gladis Pushpa Rathi , Sudharsan Engineering College , Sudharsan Engineering College , Sathiyamang', *Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 177– 187, 2019, doi: 10.19026/rjaset.10.2570.

- [12] Y. Pan et al., ‘Brain tumor grading based on Neural Networks and Convolutional Neural Networks’, Proc. Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. EMBS, vol. 2019-Novem, pp. 699–702, 2019, doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2015.7318458.
- [13] K. Meena and E. Murali, ‘Study on Various Machine Learning Algorithms for Brain Tumor Detection’, Int. J. pure Appl. Math., vol. 117, no. 8, pp. 139–143, 2019, doi: 10.12732/ijpam.v117i8.28.
- [14] S. Alaraimi, K. E. Okedu, H. Tianfield, R. Holden, and O. Uthmani, ‘Transfer learning networks with skip connections for classification of brain tumors’, Int. J. Imaging System. Technology., p. ima.22546, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1002/ima.22546.
- [15] Alycen Wiacek, Karen C. Wang, Harold Wu, Muyinatu A. Lediju Bell, ‘Photoacoustic-Guided Laparoscopic and Open Hysterectomy Procedures Demonstrated With Human Cadavers’,, p. ima.22546, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1017/ima.32786.

